

A NEW IMPREGNATION TOOL FOR ON-LINE MANUFACTURING OF THERMOPLASTIC COMPOSITES

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SUMMARY: With a newly developed impregnation tool it is possible to produce thermoplastic intermediate composite material forms such as tapes and/or to manufacture on-line, i.e. in one processing step, thermoplastic composite components. The impregnation tool is small in size, so as to be flexible for handling in front of established manufacturing processes such as pultrusion or filament-winding. Fibers and molten polymer matrix will get in contact at the outer surface of the impregnation wheel, which is the centre-piece of the impregnation tool. The molten polymer is provided from a commercial extruder. Testing of the process is illustrated by a combination of impregnation and filament-winding, in order to produce small sized tubes.

KEYWORDS: thermoplastic matrix, fibre-bundle, on-line impregnation, melt, filament-winding, pultrusion, process-combination

INTRODUCTION

Thermoplastic composites show a different property spectrum compared to thermosetting composites, which in many applications can provide advantages, such as: high fracture toughness, possibility of post-thermoforming, fast fabrication cycles and easy recycling. One interesting and new application of thermoplastic composites is the combination of different manufacturing techniques such as filament winding and injection moulding in order to carry high loads (filament wound inner part) and at the same time realize a complex shape (injection moulded outer part) [1]. However, a basic problem in manufacturing of thermoplastic composites is the fast, void free impregnation of fibre bundles or rovings with the highly viscous matrix. Many routes, such as film stacking, impregnation with thermoplastic powder, commingling of thermoplastic fibres with reinforcing fibres, or using an additional solvent to reduce the viscosity of the thermoplastic resin exist in order to overcome this problem. All of these pre-forms were necessary while manufacturing thermoplastic composites. In order to realize economic manufacturing processes it is of interest to reduce the machinery and intermediate costs. However, with the current state-of-the-art technology it is still necessary to use pre-impregnated materials which make such processes rather expensive for high volume production of pultruded or filament wound components.

This paper reports about the combination of an impregnation and a manufacturing process which is now possible because of the development of a new impregnation tool. This impregnation tool is small of size and very flexible in handling because of an open and

accessible design. The thermoplastic melt is provided from an extruder. No solvent or other additional chemicals for viscosity reduction are necessary.

BACKGROUND

Pultrusion and filament winding employing thermoplastic matrix systems have many advantages over the traditional thermosetting systems in terms of mechanical and impact behaviour, possibility of post-thermoforming, recycling and less curing time. Many more advantages but also drawbacks exist between thermoplastic and thermoset matrix materials for composite applications. The decision which kind of matrix is the most suitable one for a special part application must be determined in connection with the global demands of the part to be realized. It is false to favorite one of both matrix materials without the background of the later application. However, many advantages are in favour for thermoplastic matrices, but also disadvantages make the manufacturing processes more demanding. The most important difficulty in manufacturing continuous fibre reinforced thermoplastic composites is to gain a high degree of impregnation. This is especially true for the connection of the highly viscous and glutinous thermoplastic melt and the very slender filaments of the reinforcing material. The viscosity of the thermoplastic melt is, depending on the selected matrix, often more than two or three orders of magnitude higher in comparison to thermosets (Fig.1) [2].

Fig. 1: Viscosity values of different liquids

While the impregnation of thermosetting composites often occurs immediately in front of the manufacturing device, e.g. in filament winding and pultrusion processes, this could not be achieved so far with thermoplastic matrices in an economic range. The reasons are not only the difficult impregnation because of the high viscosity of the melt, it is also difficult to handle the heated melt and all the machinery parts, that must be heated. To overcome these problems it is up to now state-of-the-art to separate the impregnation and manufacturing processes. The impregnation of thermoplastic composite intermediates itself is divided into many different techniques, and a few of them are described in the following: In an overview,

the totally impregnated intermediates like tapes or organic sheets and the semi-impregnated intermediates like powder impregnated fibre bundles, commingled fibre bundles or cowoven mats must be separated. The main difference between these two groups is that the impregnation step is completely finished (in the tapes and organic sheets) in contrast to the semi-impregnated intermediates which are not really impregnated. In this case only the fibres and the matrix material are mixed in such a way that the distribution of the matrix and the fibres is optimized in order to reduce the way of flow for the melt when the matrix is molten. Figure 2 gives an overview of the most important impregnation techniques.

Fig. 2: Impregnation techniques

The main drawback of the semi-impregnated intermediates is that the impregnation does not occur before the part processing takes place. The consequence is that the impregnation quality is not easy to control. The degree of impregnation of the totally impregnated composite intermediates is close to those of the manufactured parts. For filament winding processes with tape e.g. it is not necessary to heat up the complete tape, but it is enough to heat the contact zone right in front of the nip-point between tape and the already wound structure [3]. Therefore it is possible to achieve higher processing speeds.

An additional drawback of the pre-impregnated intermediates is that the users are restricted to the materials which are on the market available. That means, the composition of fibre and matrix material, the fibre volume content, the colour and all the other qualities are depending on the suppliers offer. Up to now only a few different kinds of thermoplastic composite intermediates are available. This limits the application development despite the many advantages of a thermoplastic matrix. Additionally, the cost of the long fibre reinforced thermoplastic composite intermediates is higher, compared to the material costs for thermosetting composites.

The aim for this research project was to overcome these mentioned drawbacks for thermoplastic composites and to develop a new process which combines the impregnation and the manufacturing process.

DEVELOPMENT OF A SUITABLE IMPREGNATION PROCESS

To be not depend on the special offers of intermediate material suppliers, raw materials for thermoplastic composite parts should be generally available. It is possible to choose from a very large amount of suppliers of fibres and matrices when direct melt impregnation is used. Additionally, the direct impregnation via melt compared to other techniques mentioned above has the advantage, that no “preprocessing” of the matrix except of melting is necessary. To produce a high-quality composite it is important to realize a high degree of impregnation without any voids or defects. At this point the existing melt impregnation techniques are discussed, in order to find out their strengths and weaknesses:

In one commonly used melt impregnation technique for fibre rovings today, the impregnation is carried out by feeding fibre bundles alongside a number of pins which are situated in a heated bath of molten polymer matrix (Figure 3) [4].

Fig. 3: The melt bath impregnation technique

However some drawbacks are connected to this technique, which are: (a) fibre damage caused by physical contact with the pins, (b) fibre tension generated by the diversion of the fibre bundle together with the high sliding friction (caused by the presence of viscous melt at the surface of the pins), and (c) that the impregnation step takes only place when the fibre bundles are in contact with the pins. This “melt bath”-technique has also been studied by several research groups and qualitative and quantitative models exist to describe the tension build up in the fibre bundles and the impregnation process in this technique [5,6]. This understanding can be used to optimize the melt bath impregnation technique, yet the basic drawbacks of this process related to the high fibre tension, the very sensitive process and the short impregnation time need further attention. Negative for a combination with a filament winding or pultrusion process is the large geometric size and weight of the melt bath. Additionally, the close design makes an easy set up (change of fibre bundles or matrix material) difficult. For a filament winding process the achievable processing speeds are low and not economic enough.

Another melt impregnation process exists of two or more dies in which a nozzle supports the melt through the fibre bundle. Also in this process the impregnation takes place in a short time step in which the fibre bundle crosses the nozzle. A high fibre tension must be generated in order to keep the fibre bundle in contact with the dies, so that the melt can penetrate

perpendicular through it. Figure 4 shows a schematic drawing of this impregnation process [7].

Fig. 4: The melt injection impregnation technique

The main drawback is the high fibre tension that must be adjusted in the manner that the fibre bundle is in contact with the dies. The impregnation time is very short. An impregnation can only take place when the fibres pass the nozzle. The pressure of the melt must be very high to ensure that the high flow resistance of the fibre bundle can be exceeded.

The evaluation of these melt impregnation techniques with a simple mathematical equation shows which are the most important parameters for a penetration process:

Darcy's law describes the basic parameters of a penetration process through a porous medium (such as a fibre bundle). The value of the penetration speed v_{Matrix} of a liquid medium is described as:

$$v_{Matrix} = \frac{K}{\eta} \cdot \frac{\Delta p_{FB}}{\Delta l_{FB}}$$

where Δl_{FB} is the thickness of the fibre bundle, η the viscosity of the polymer melt, K a geometric constant, and Δp_{FB} the pressure difference. The integration shows the depth of penetration z in function of these parameters: [6]:

$$z = \sqrt{\frac{K \cdot 2 \cdot t_i \cdot \Delta p_{FB}}{\eta}}$$

When all constants are combined to one constant (z is also constant and equal to the bundle thickness) only the relevant variables of penetration are shown:

$$const = \frac{t_i \cdot \Delta p_{FB}}{\eta}$$

It is now recognizable for a high value of this constant (equal to a better impregnation) that these three parameters of impregnation are the most important ones. The viscosity should be low, whereas the time of impregnation and the melt pressure should be high.

For both impregnation processes described the real time of impregnation is very short. In case of the melt bath technique it takes place only in front of the contact zone with the pins [6], while using the melt injection, impregnation occurs only in the range of the nozzle. Because of the short impregnation time, the melt pressure must be high so as to realize equal impregnation depths. Therefore the value of fibre bundle tension must also be high to keep the filaments in close contact with the nozzle. To overcome these geometric and theoretical drawbacks a new impregnation tool was developed which unites all the important conditions.

NEW IMPREGNATION TOOL AND PROCESS COMBINATION

The aims of the new tool design for impregnation of fibre bundles with a thermoplastic melt were: (a) to verify a longer impregnation time, thus allowing a higher line speeds (out-put), (b) to prevent the build up of high fibre tension, (c) to allow easy and smooth processing of the fibre bundles (no sharp diversion angles), even when a number of broken filaments exists in the fibre bundle (decreasing the sensitivity of the process), and (d) to design a simple structure of the tool in order to allow fast set up times, easy handling, and the possibility to situate it in front of a manufacturing process. All of these criteria could be met by the new tool (impregnation wheel) (Figure 5)[8].

Fig. 5: The new impregnation tool (impregnation wheel)

The impregnation wheel consists of a ring, which allows the molten thermoplastic matrix to penetrate through it and through the fibre bundle, which is pulled between a supporting rail

system placed at the edges of the wheel. The fibre bundle is in physical contact with the outer surface of the ring along half of its perimeter (up to 180°), and this section of the ring is permeable. By increasing the diameter of the impregnation wheel, the duration of the impregnation step can be largely extended. This means that the effective impregnation time t_i is much longer compared to the processes described above. Because of the high shear rate while the molten polymer matrix penetrates through the porous material the viscosity η is reduced to a minimum value. Therefore, the impregnation pressure Δp_{FB} can be reduced to reach a lower fibre bundle tension which reduces fibre damages due to the impregnation step. The latter allows to produce high quality impregnated fibre bundles. As this wheel is positioned right in front of the pultrusion die or the filament winding mandrel, it is not only possible to precisely control the winding or pultrusion temperature but also to vary the fibre volume fraction within a certain range. Because of the fully molten polymer, the impregnated fibre bundle is completely welded with the surface of the wound layer manufactured before, or to the neighbouring strands during pultrusion. This design therefore promises high output due to the adjustable impregnation time, no or low fibre bundle tensioning due to its low diversion (by the large diameter of the wheel), and short set up times as well as easy handling due to the fact that there are no dies through which the fibre bundle has to be pulled through. The fibre volume fraction is adjusted by controlling the amount of molten polymer.

The station has to be placed next to a commercially available extruder that provides the molten polymer through a flexible heated tube, thus feeding the molten matrix into the impregnation tool. The impregnation head was built in a small size to allow attachment to commercial filament winding supports (Figure 6). It is very easy to change or replace the fibre bundles in short times. In addition, it will be attempted soon to adjust the impregnation tool to an existing thermoplastic pultrusion line.

Fig. 6: Principle of the combined impregnation and filament-winding process

CHARACTERIZATION OF MANUFACTURED PARTS

All these advantages are demonstrated on the example of filament wound tubes (Figure 7).

Fig. 7: On-line impregnated and wound tubes

The inner perimeter of these tubes was 70mm and the length up to 700mm. The materials used in the study were three glass fiber bundles, each with 1200 tex and different matrix polymers (e.g. PP; PE; PA12). Microscopic inspections of polished samples obtained by these winding tests showed that a satisfactory impregnation quality is achievable. However, optimisation of the governing processing parameters is expected to further improve the quality of the wound parts. In these first test runs only winding angles of 90° were realized. The determination of the degree of impregnation was carried out by embedding three samples (which were taken from different positions of the wound tube) into an epoxy resin. After curing and polishing, the degree of impregnation was determined by the ratio of the impregnated fibers to all counted fibers in the analyzed surface of a sample (cross section of the tube). One polished surface of an impregnated fibre bundle embedded in epoxy is presented in Figure 8.

Figure 8. A cross section sample of a wound tube, manufactured with the combined impregnation and winding process (PP-GF winding speed: 5m/min)

CONCLUSIONS

A new process consisting of a new melt impregnation tool, the so called “impregnation wheel”, in combination with a common manufacturing process is presented; it shows some promising and innovative manufacturing aspects. The combination makes processing of continuous fibre reinforced thermoplastic composites in one manufacturing step possible; it is therefore very attractive from an economic stand point. Compared to other existing techniques it is now possible to save the cost for manufacturing intermediates and to be free in combining various fibre and matrix materials. Generally the measured degrees of impregnation of the wound glass fibre reinforced PP-tubes are very high. Hence the results presented here allow to speculate, that higher processing speeds together with a high degree of impregnation can be realized with further optimization of this new processing facility.

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